

Later Hellenistic silver coinages of western and southern Asia Minor

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Unlike some other speakers at the conference, I was not involved in the selection of coins to be analysed; nor do the coins I have been asked to comment on form a coherent numismatic category as some other groups do.² Therefore, the focus of this paper may loosely be described as silver coin produced in western and southern Asia Minor from the late 3rd-1st centuries BC, which in general does not explicitly identify itself as royal.³ The majority of the coins have the appearance of civic coins, by which I mean that they have iconography specific or appropriate to a civic issuer, as well as a legend identifying the city of issue.⁴ However, in a number of cases their 'civic' nature may be contested, and indeed is one aspect of their production that it may be useful to test through chemical analysis. A small number are issues of the Lycian League.

I. Historical background and periodization

Given the variety of coins within the group under consideration, in terms of possible agency (civic, royal, league), geography (Troas, Aeolis, Ionia, Caria, Lycia, Pamphylia) and chronology (3rd, 2nd and 1st centuries BC), it is plainly necessary to apply some sort of a-prioristic framework within which to discuss the analytic results. To this end, my approach has been to apply a hypothetical periodization to the data and what I intend to do in this paper is to take a look at the analytical results within that framework, using a series of charts that Professor Ponting has produced. I should note at the outset that I do not think that it is possible to offer any firm conclusions at this point. The small samples available elicit no great confidence, and patterns are far from always clear. Nonetheless, I hope that certain observations that can be made on the basis of this data can serve as hypotheses for further testing. Moreover, it is the

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² I must begin by expressing my gratitude to Professors Butcher and Ponting for the invitation to take a look at the results of their analyses of the coinage from western and southern Asia Minor. I was not involved in the initial choice of coins to be analysed. For this credit must go to Kevin himself and Richard Ashton, who was unable to attend the conference in Rome for health reasons. The opportunity to work on this material was particularly welcome as it dovetails so well with my own ERC project, CHANGE: The development of the monetary economy of ancient Anatolia, c. 630-30 BC. My work on this article was thus completed as part of that project with funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant agreement No. 865680).

³ A full catalogue is provided in Part II of this paper. The one exception to this description is a tetradrachm of King Amyntas of Galatia.

⁴ The exception is the coinage of Side which bears no ethnic, only magistrate's names or initials.

great merit of the RACOM project that it casts its net very wide. I hope that some at least of what we can see in this data may find points of comparison in those being considered by others. The first task, then, is to explain the periodization that I have adopted.

1. The Seleucid *Reconquista*

The first group of coins, one of Antioch-Alabanda and four of Side were all produced c. 200 BC. The Sidetan coins, I have suggested in an earlier article, were produced as part of the naval re-activation of Side in Pamphylia by Antiochus III for his fleet in the last years of the 3rd century (the types echoing those of Alexander the Great referring to his own adoption of the title ‘Megas’ at this time).⁵ The Series 1 coinage of Antioch-Alabanda, I will argue in a forthcoming book, was similarly inaugurated by Antiochus as part of his re-connection with the Seleucid foundations of western Asia Minor, which included at Alabanda the espousal of the city’s claim to *asylia* in c. 202 BC.

2. The Return of ‘Civic’ Coinage

The second group of coins belongs to the middle part of the 2nd century BC. Civic coinage in silver had largely disappeared in Asia Minor in the third century BC,⁶ but re-emerges with some vigour in the mid second century BC, looking quite different from its classical forebears.⁷ Three different phenomena can be identified. The first of these is the well-known case of the wreathed tetradrachms of a number of cities. We have analyses for one such coin of Aegae, four coins of Cyme, seven of Myrina and one of Magnesia. In addition we have one analysis of a drachm of Herakleia Latmos, which seems to be contemporary with the wreathed coinage of that city, and 5 drachms and hemidrachms of Myndos in Caria, which may accompany the small wreathed coinage produced there. These coinages were all perhaps struck within a period of twenty years or less (Fig. 1). The major historical debates around these coinages have concerned questions of agency and function. Were these civic coinages, as their appearance suggests? Were

⁵ Meadows 2009, pp. 80-81.

⁶ Meadows 2021b.

⁷ For an overview see Meadows 2018.

they royal, perhaps Attalid, coinages in disguise (“too big to be civic”, as Callataÿ has articulated it, in some cases)?⁸ And why do they largely end up in Syria?⁹

165	160	155	150	145	140
			AEGAE (C)		
CYME (A)		CYME (C)			
MYRINA (A)	MYRINA (C)				
			MAGNESIA (C)		
				HERAKLEIA (C)	
		MYNDOS (C)			

Fig. 1. Relative chronologies of selected 2nd-century BC ‘civic’ coinages¹⁰

A second, and perhaps related phenomenon is the re-emergence of Sidetan coinage at around the same time. Issued in the name of the same magistrate, Kleuch(ares), who had apparently struck the last of the early tetradrachms of Side, these appear to be imitations. I have suggested that these ‘Kleuchares II’ issues may also be royal issues, this time produced by the Attalid kings to fund their absorption of Pamphylia.¹¹

And finally there is the curious phenomenon of cistophoric weight civic coinages produced at a handful of mints in the 2nd century.¹² Among the analysed coins, we have just one specimen of Alabanda. But the existence of these issues reminds us that the composition of Attalid cistophori will be important comparanda for all of the civic coinage of this period.

3. ‘Mithridatic’

The next period I have called, quite tendentiously, Mithridatic, on the assumption that the period of the First Mithridatic War (89-85 BC) must have seen an uptick in the production of silver coinage, and that we can perhaps associate several intriguing coinages with this increase. I have assigned four specimens to this period: a late wreathed issue of Abydos the chronology of which has been discussed by Callataÿ;¹³ a tetradrachm of Alexandria Troas that is explicitly

⁸ Callataÿ 2011.

⁹ For recent discussions of their nature, size and deposition see Psoma 2013, Callataÿ 2013 and Duyrat 2016, esp. pp. 374-9. For the coinage of Myndos see Meadows and Zabel 2002.

¹⁰ (C) = civic issues; (A) = Alexanders. For the chronologies see Meadows & Houghton 2010, Meadows & Zabel 2002 and Ellis-Evans and Özdizbay 2020.

¹¹ Meadows 2006, 158-161 and 2013, pp. 187-8.

¹² The evidence is collected by Ashton 2013.

¹³ Callataÿ 1996

dated to 85 BC;¹⁴ a tetradrachm of Side in the name of Kleuchares of my group III, which I have argued on grounds of metrology probably belongs to the first half of the first century BC;¹⁵ and, finally, a drachm (or perhaps denarius) of Aphrodisias, which the thin evidence that exists also suggests may belong to the first half of the 1st century BC.¹⁶

4. Civil Wars

Fourth comes a period that I have dubbed ‘Civil Wars’. Essentially it consists of two coins: a ‘hemidrachm’ minted at the Carian city of Tabai. This is surely a coin of the 40s BC, and struck to the standard of the Roman quinarius;¹⁷ and a ‘tetradrachm’ of Sidetan types, signed by Mark Antony’s appointee to the kingdom of Galatia, Amyntas. With a weight of around 15.83g, this is clearly not to be regarded as an Attic weight tetradrachm coinage, but is perhaps best regarded as a 4 *denarius* piece. In any case it plainly belongs to the 30s BC.¹⁸

5. The Lycian League to Augustus

Finally, I note here that some other coins were analysed, when they were too small to be drilled, by muon analysis.¹⁹ These do not provide the same elemental breakdowns, but do provide figures for silver content. These analyses are scattered over the various chronological groups, but one body of material can be usefully extracted for consideration comprised of 7 coins of the Lycian league. These allow us an overview that extends down into a fifth period, which we may call Augustan.²⁰

¹⁴ For the chronology of this series see, most recently, Ellis-Evans 2016, p. 127 with n. 45.

¹⁵ Meadows 2006, pp. 161-4.

¹⁶ See the summary at Meadows 2021a, p. 177 n. 62.

¹⁷ See the discussion at Meadows 2021a, pp. 173-6.

¹⁸ Meadows 2015, pp. 419-20; 2021a, p. 166.

¹⁹ See the chapter by Dr. Adrian Hillier in this volume.

²⁰ The latest issues are of Troxell 1982’s Period IV, series 6, bearing portraits of Augustus.

II. The Results²¹

Fig. 2. Simple Dot Plot of Weights by Group and Mint

We may begin with a general plot of fineness across the whole sample, divided by period and coloured for each mint (Fig. 2). In general little change in fineness is observable across the periods. The exception is clearly the wreathed coinages (Aegeae, Cyme, Myrina, Magnesia, Heracleia), where a marked inconsistency and diminution is evident. At the lower end of the scale here (75%) we should note that the silver content of these coins is close to that of the contemporary cistophori, which weigh 75% of an Attic-weight tetradrachm, but were, as the RACOM results show, being minted with very high silver content.²²

Proceeding to the trace element analyses it will be useful to take a look first at the results by period, before proceeding to a comparison of them and possible conclusions and/or suggestions for further work. For each period, two charts are presented, one showing the ratios of gold to bismuth scaled to silver, the other with lead to bismuth.

²¹ For the methods employed to analyse these coinages, see the chapter by Matthew Ponting in the present volume.

²² See the chapter by Lucia Carbone in the present volume.

1. Seleucid *Reconquista*

In the first two charts (Figs. 3 and 4) I have circled two groups of coinage. Under the *reconquista* are shown the results for a tetradrachm of Alabanda and four early tetradrachms of Side:

Alabanda

Obv. Head of Apollo Isotimos. *Rev.* Pegasus. Meadows 2008 series 1.

Y1823 Yale 2001.87.7201 ANTIOXEΩN ΔHMHTPIOΣ.

Side

Obv. Head of Athena in crested crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Nike holding a wreath; pomegranate Leschhorn 1989, nos. 1-23.

Y1832 Yale 2004.6.3165 XPY
 Y1833 Yale 2001.87.10608 Σ-T
 Y1835 Yale 2004.6.3167 ΔΙΟΔ
 Y1836 Yale 2004.6.3166 ΣΤΗ

Compared with these are the results for 4 tetradrachms in the name of Side from the mid second century BC:

Obv. Head of Athena in crested crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Nike holding a wreath; pomegranate. Meadows 2006, Kleuchares II.

Y1834 Yale 2004.6.3164 ΚΑΕ-ΥΧ
 Y1837 Yale 2001.87.11676 ΚΑΕ-ΥΧ
 Y1838 Yale 2001.87.11677 ΚΑΕ-ΥΧ
 Y1839 Yale 2001.87.11678 ΚΑΕ-ΥΧ

Fig. 3. Period 1 (*Reconquista*), gold vs. bismuth

Fig. 4. Period 1 (Reconquista), lead vs. bismuth

There is a plausible grouping for the reconquista issues in their gold content. Perhaps more striking is that the issues of Side of this period look different to ‘Side’ issues of Kleuchares II of the mid 2nd century (below, Figs. 5-6), supporting the conclusion arrived at on the basis of hoard evidence that these are different coinages.

2. The Return of ‘Civic’ Coinage

In this category we are looking at the results both for a number of ‘wreathed’ issues as well as a civic coinage of Myndos in Caria, which also dates to the second century BC. We may also add the Kleuchares II coinage of Side, listed above, to the comparison, since it seems to belong chronologically in the same window.

Myndos

Obv. Head of Serapis wearing the Atef wreath. *Rev.* Basileion (feathered and horned wreath of Hathor); in the lower field, two corn-ears. Drachms, Meadows and Zabel 2002, groups a-b.

PU2002-52	Princeton	ΣΩΣΤΡΑΤΟΣ
PU2004-9	Princeton	ΗΡΟΔΩΡΟΣ

Obv. Head of Dionysus wearing a vine wreath. *Rev.* Winged thunderbolt. Hemidrachms, Meadows and Zabel 2002, group c.

PU1997-10	Princeton	ΙΕΡΟΚΛΗΣ
PU1995-52	Princeton	ΠΕΙΘΙΑΣ
PU1996-34	Princeton	ΚΑΛΛΙΚΛΗΣ

Aegae

Obv. Head of Apollo wearing a laurel wreath; in the left field, bow and quiver. *Rev.* Zeus naked, holding an eagle and a sceptre; all in an oak wreath. Tetradrachm, Meadows, forthcoming, D3

Y1814 Yale 2001.87.11656 $\overline{\text{A}}$

Kyme

Obv. Head of the Kyme Amazon wearing a sphenone and a bun. *Rev.* Horse walking wearing a bridle; between legs, vase with one handle; all in an olive wreath. Tetradrachms, Oakley 1982.

Y1815	Yale	ΚΑΛΛΙΑΣ
PU2869	Princeton	ΚΑΛΛΙΑΣ
Y1816	Yale	ΟΛΥΜΠΙΟΣ
W566	Winterthur	ΣΕΥΘΗΣ
Y1817	Yale	ΑΜΦΙΚΤΥΩΝ
PU1995-16	Princeton	ΑΜΦΙΚΤΥΩΝ

Myrina

Obv. Head of Apollo wearing a laurel wreath, braided hair. *Rev.* Apollo of Grynium wearing a laurel wreath and himation, holding a phiale and a ribboned branch; in the lower field, omphalos and amphora; all in a laurel wreath. Tetradrachms, Sacks 1985.

Y1821	Yale	Sacks 3
W567	Winterthur	Sacks 18
Y1818	Yale	Sacks 20
Y1819	Yale	Sacks 22
Y1822	Yale	Sacks 26
PU1995-17	Princeton	Sacks 29
Y1820	Yale	Sacks 45

Heraclea ad Latmum

Obv. Head of Athena wearing a crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Club in an oak wreath. Lavva 1993, 1-13.

PU1995-18 Princeton Lavva 1993, 1-13.

Magnesia ad Maeandrum

Obv. Bust of Artemis draped wearing a diadem, a quiver on the shoulder. *Rev.* Apollo on a meander pattern, naked, leaning on a tripod; all in a laurel wreath. Jones 1979.

W570 Winterthur ΕΥΦΗΜΟΣ ΠΑΥΣΑΝΙΟΥ

Fig. 5. Period 2 ('Civic'), gold vs. bismuth

Fig. 6. Period 2 ('Civic'), lead vs. bismuth

Breaking down the 2nd century coinages into constituent parts perhaps serves to highlight the anomalous nature of the wreathed coinages, which show little apparent similarity. Both Kyme and Myrina show little homogeneity of composition. Comparison with the two other coinages may be more interesting. In terms of lead content it seems clear that the drachm coinage of Myndos looks very different from the wreathed coinages. This matches the picture from the

plot weights. The wreathed coinages and the Myndian smaller denomination coinage appear to be different phenomena. The coinage of Kleuchares II seems to present a different phenomenon again, which is perhaps not surprising if it was produced geographically apart from the other coinages, possibly in Pamphylia.

3. Mithridatic

Just six analyses are available for this period: three from Caria, two from the Troad, and another Sidetan imitation. The coins are listed below, and the charts of analyses examined in section 4 below (Figs. 7-8).

Abydos

Obv. Diademed and draped bust of Artemis, right; bow and quiver over left shoulder. *Rev.* Eagle standing right, wings spread; within laurel wreath. Tetradrachm, Callataÿ 1996, p. 87.

PU2001-108 Princeton

ΘΕΣΠΙΔΟΣ

Alexandria Troas

Obv. Head of Apollo laureate. *Rev.* Apollo Smintheus standing right, quiver on shoulder, holding bow, arrow and patera. Tetradrachm, Bellinger 1961.

W565

Winterthur

ΑΝΤΑΙΟΥ ΣΙΣ

Aphrodisias

Obv. Bust of Aphrodite wearing a veil and a stephane (crown). *Rev.* Eagle on a thunderbolt, wings closed. Drachm, MacDonald 1992, 2-26.

W572

Winterthur

ΞΕΝΟΚΡΑΤΗΣ ΞΕΝΟΚΡΑΤΟΥ

Stratonikeia

Obv. Head of Hekate. *Rev.* Nike advancing holding a wreath and a palm over her shoulder. Drachm, Meadows 2002, group 3.

ET4481

Winterthur

ΔΙΟΦΑΝΤΟΣ, omphalos with serpent (?)

Obv. Head of Zeus wearing a laurel wreath *Rev.* Eagle facing. Hemidrachm, Meadows 2002, group 3.

ET4581

Winterthur

ΧΡΥΣΟΙ

Side

Obv. Head of Athena in crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Nike holding a wreath; pomegranate. Meadows 2006, Kleuchares III.

Y1839

Yale

2001.87.11678

ΚΛΕΥΧ

4. Civil War

By this period silver coinage is rare in southern Asia Minor, and just three coins were analysed: two of Tabae in Caria and one produced by Amyntas of Galatia with the types used earlier by the city of Side. The weight standard of both coinages seems to be influenced by the Roman denarius. The former, often described as hemidrachms are in fact Roman *quinarii*, the latter, although taking the form of an Attic weight tetradrachm coinage in fact appear to be produced at the weight of four *denarii*.²³

Tabae

Obv. Head of Athena wearing a crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Nike advancing holding a wreath and a palm over her shoulder. Robert and Robert 1954, pp. 124-5, Group C.

W574 **Winterthur** KAA
 ET3594 Private collection BPAXYAIΔΑΣ

Amyntas of Galatia

Obv. Head of Athena in crested Corinthian helmet. *Rev.* Nike holding a wreath; pomegranate. *RPC* I. 3501.

Y1840 Yale 2001.87.11583

Fig. 8. Period 3 and 4 (Mithridatic and Civil War), lead vs. bismuth

The analyses for these two first-century groups of coinages (Figs. 7-8) look very different to the second century (Figs. 5-6). There is a very tight concentration for both of the first-century periods, which seem close to each other too.

5. Some tentative conclusions

The overall view of the results may best be viewed by combining the above charts in two more (Figs. 9-10). The size of the sample, as we have noted, is very small, but some trends emerge that, while falling short of firm conclusions, may be suggestive of potential future directions of research. First, we note the relatively tight clustering of *Reconquista* issues, particularly by gold content. This may be suggestive of a common stock being used at two of Antiochus III's mints in the very late 3rd century BC. Clearly, it would be interesting to carry out analyses on other coinages of explicitly Seleucid type from the Seleucid west, to see if these fit a broader pattern. It would be equally interesting to extend such a programme to the numerous posthumous Alexander coinages of this period to see the degree to which we might be looking at a much broader financing of the Seleucid *reconquista* from similar bullion sources.

The second century sees relatively tight clustering for the issues of Kleuchares II, suggesting, perhaps, a relatively controlled source of silver for this coinage. It can also be seen, by comparison with the results analysed by Carbone in this volume, that in terms of both lead and gold content, the Kleuchares II issues fall squarely within the broad cluster exhibited by the Attalid cistophoric coinage.²⁴ This certainly fits with the idea that this was a local Attalid coinage produced within Pamphylia, though it cannot be said to prove it. The remainder of the second century coinages show far less homogeneity, and perhaps suggest coinages being produced from silver drawn from a varied supply of coinages, or other sources of bullion. Very tentatively we might suggest that the wreathed coinages do not appear to have been struck from the same bullion stock as the contemporary and neighbouring Attalid cistophoric coinages. This does not necessarily rule out the Attalid involvement in the wreathed issues that has been suggested by some. However, if the wreathed issues were of Attalid inspiration, we must perhaps posit separate production and bullion source. Again, more analyses from a wider range of mints would be most useful. Finally, a certain degree of homogeneity re-emerges in the coinages of the first century BC, when there may be some cause to see Roman involvement in their production. Does this mean new silver sources appearing in Asia Minor with the arrival of Roman armies in the great conflicts against Mithridates and between the Roman *imperatores*? Again, we must wait for more evidence from Asia Minor and beyond. But it is a credit to the RACOM project that we may now begin to see the questions to ask.

²⁴ The gold is more variable for the mid to later-c2 cistophori, but the Side coins seem to fall within their range. See Carbone Fig. 3 The Sidetan lead content is generally low, 1 or under, in both (apart from Y1837 for Kleuchares II), in contrast to the cistophori of the first century, which have variable lead levels. See Carbone Fig. 21.

Fig. 9. All periods compared, gold vs. bismuth

Fig. 10. All periods compared, lead vs. bismuth

Appendix. The Lycian League

We may also take a look at the coinage of the Lycian League, which has been analysed only by Muon analysis, and for which, therefore, we only have percentages of silver content (Fig. 11). Again, paucity of data requires caution, but the pattern, such as it is, suggests true Lycian coinage of the cities (Troxell issues 26 and 51) is purest, at 96%. An interestingly low result of

88% emerges for the contemporary pseudo-League coinage of Olympos. In the coinage that I have suggested elsewhere may belong to the Mithridatic period (Troxell issues 110 and 133), we seem to have a dip in fineness, with results of 92 and 88.2%, but then there is mixed picture in the didrachm issues with Augustan portraits (Troxell issues 111, 116 and 121), with results varying wildly from 85-95%.²⁵

Fig. 11. Lycian League coinages. Silver content (Muon analysis).

²⁵ For the relative and absolute chronology of Troxell's Period IV, see Meadows in Ashton and Meadows (2008), pp. 113-6.

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